

Diving into Software Evolution: Virtual Reality vs. On-Screen

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Abstract—Background: Traditional 2D visualizations have been widely used for software metrics and evolution analysis, offering structured views of complex data. However, the advent of Virtual Reality (VR) technologies introduces new possibilities for immersive and interactive software visualization, potentially enhancing comprehension and user engagement.

Objective/Aim: This report aims to evaluate the effectiveness of VR immersive visualizations compared to traditional 2D on-screen visualizations for understanding code metrics across software releases. Specifically, we seek to determine if VR provides better accuracy and speed for comprehending high-level software evolution tasks.

Method: We will conduct a controlled experiment with 30 participants from academia and industry, using GitLab, GitHub, or an IDE for on-screen visualizations and a VR setup using Meta Quest 3. Tasks related to software evolution will be completed in both settings. Accuracy and time will be measured and analyzed using mixed linear models and non-parametric tests to compare the two approaches. Data will be sourced from GitHub repositories with similar project characteristics.

Index Terms—city metaphor, software evolution, software visualization, CODECITY, data visualization, virtual reality

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional 2D visualizations have been the cornerstone for analyzing software evolution and code metrics, offering structured and intuitive views of complex data. However, VR technologies have sparked interest in their potential for software visualization. VR offers unique advantages in spatial cognition and immersive interaction, potentially enhancing software system comprehension.

Among various 3D visualization techniques, the city metaphor stands out [1]. Initially proposed by Munro *et al.* [2] and refined by Wettel *et al.* [3], CODECITY transforms object-oriented software systems into explorable cities [4]. Software metrics map to features like building height, size, and color, providing locality and supporting orientation while preserving structural complexity [5].

Typically, treemaps position buildings hierarchically, effectively showing complex structures and bottlenecks [6]. However, they struggle with representing software evolution due to layout recalculations. The spiral algorithm addresses this by incorporating new elements without disrupting visual continuity [7].

Recent advancements in VR and web technologies open new avenues for software visualization. VR offers an immersive experience, allowing users to explore software systems as if physically present. Web-based VR tools democratize access to advanced visualization techniques for a broader audience.

This report proposes a controlled experiment to compare **2D on-screen vs. VR immersive visualization** of code metrics. The primary objective is to determine if VR immersion is as effective and efficient as 2D visualization for the same data. We will design comprehension tasks, analyze answer accuracy, and measure the time taken. Building on previous studies [8], [9], which showed significant results, this experiment further explores VR's potential benefits. The first study [8] compared on-screen and VR CODECITY for static software representations, while the second [9] evaluated VR's impact on understanding code review processes by replicating on-screen dashboards in VR.

While these studies provided valuable insights into VR benefits for static and dynamic software visualization, the current experiment focuses on code metrics evolution over multiple releases. This longitudinal analysis offers a comprehensive understanding of software evolution, complementing our previous work and contributing to broader knowledge of VR's capabilities and limitations.

II. BACKGROUND

A. 2D Code Visualizations

Visualizing complex data ecosystems, such as software repositories, is crucial for modern software development and maintenance [10]. Traditionally, this information has been presented in tabular or textual formats, which, while structured, may not fully capture intricate relationships.

2D visualizations offer a more intuitive view of software systems, allowing users to see the entire system at a glance and identify critical areas for modification. These visualizations provide a common language for developers and data scientists, facilitating effective communication and collaboration. Integrated Development Environments (IDEs) such as Visual Studio Code, IntelliJ IDEA, and Eclipse, along with platforms like GitHub and GitLab [11]–[13], include tools for visualizing code metrics over time [14], [15]. These tools help track changes and analyze the historical context of codebases [16].

Graphical representations such as heatmaps, line charts, and bar charts are commonly used to depict various code metrics, including lines of code, code churn, and complexity [17]. Tools like SonarQube and CodeClimate integrate these visualizations to assist developers in identifying code quality issues and trends over time [18]. These visual tools enable developers to pinpoint hotspots in the codebase that may require refactoring or additional testing [19].

In the context of software repositories, 2D visualizations provide valuable insights into the structure and complexity of the codebase, guiding decision-making processes. However, as software systems become increasingly complex, there is a growing need for more immersive and intuitive techniques, such as 3D and VR visualizations. This report aims to explore this potential by evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of VR visualizations compared to traditional 2D on-screen tools.

B. VR BABIAXR Evolving City Visualization

The goal of a VR environment is to harness its immersive and spatial capabilities. For developing VR visualizations, we will utilize A-Frame, creating a dynamic scene to visualize the time evolution of CODECITY. BABIAXR provides a diverse range of 3D visualizations, such as bars, cylinders, and bubbles, which represent depth, height, and width, allowing for a richer representation of data compared to conventional 2D visualizations. Additionally, A-Frame supports 3D treemap visualizations, which can effectively represent the city metaphor for code visualization. Figure 1 illustrates an example of the scenes that can be created using A-Frame. While this figure does not depict the exact scene to be used in our experiment, it provides a general idea of the advanced visualizations that extend beyond traditional 2D tools, making full use of the three-dimensional space. For instance, a 3D bars map in A-Frame can aggregate multiple 2D bar chart visualizations into a comprehensive VR representation.

Fig. 1: Example of a BABIAXR scene

Specifically, we have developed BABIAXR-CODECITY within A-Frame to visualize the time evolution of software using the city metaphor layout. The VR scene in BABIAXR-CODECITY includes an interactive navigation bar that allows users to navigate through different time instants, showcasing the evolution of the city. This navigation bar is designed to be user-friendly and intuitive, enabling users to customize

the direction and speed of time progression or make non-sequential jumps through the timeline. As users interact with the navigation bar, the city dynamically updates, with new structures appearing transparently and disappearing structures being promptly removed, ensuring a seamless understanding of the evolving city. Inspired by multimedia navigation interfaces, this design offers a robust tool for controlling software evolution visualizations, promoting user exploration and experimentation (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Example of a BABIAXR time evolving city

C. Related studies

Software Evolution. The study of software evolution focuses on the processes by which software systems change over time, encompassing aspects such as maintenance, enhancement, and adaptation to new requirements. Lehman’s laws of software evolution provide foundational principles, highlighting that software must continuously evolve or become progressively less useful [20]. Research in this area often examines metrics like code complexity, churn, and refactoring practices to understand and predict software behavior over time [21]. Tools and visualizations have been developed to aid in the analysis of software evolution, offering insights into the impact of changes and guiding maintenance activities [22]. Comprehensive studies have explored how these visualizations help in maintaining software quality and managing technical debt [23].

Virtual Reality. Virtual Reality (VR) has shown significant potential in enhancing spatial understanding in various fields, such as analyzing brain tumors [24], interpreting shapes and forms [25], studying paleontology [26], exploring caves [27], and conducting magnetic resonance imaging [28]. The ability of VR to facilitate multidimensional analysis makes it particularly useful for large datasets. Extensive research has been conducted on the application of VR for visualizing scientific data across numerous domains [29]–[32]. Bryson [33] highlighted the advantages of VR for interacting with complex phenomena and visualizing intricate data sets. Although 2D visualization remains the standard, the gradual integration of 3D and VR visualizations has been notable. While some researchers have warned against the unnecessary use of 3D visualizations [34], others have advocated for the benefits that 3D and VR bring to data visualization [35]–[37]. The city metaphor for

software visualization, introduced by Munro *et al.* [2] and later expanded by Wettel *et al.* [3], has been effectively explored within VR environments, with CityVR [38] being a prominent example. Our team has also conducted experiments comparing this visualization in both on-screen and VR settings, providing valuable insights into their respective effectiveness [8], [9].

III. EXPERIMENT PLANNING

A. Goal

The primary objective of this experiment is to determine whether the comprehension of software system evolution, as visualized through code metrics, is more effective in Virtual Reality (VR) environments compared to traditional 2D screen-based visualizations.

B. Participants and Settings

The experiment will involve at least 30 participants from both academic (students and researchers) and industrial backgrounds. All participants will undergo a preliminary screening through a questionnaire to ensure they possess a minimum level of knowledge about software development. Only those who pass this screening will be included in the experiment. The participants will be unrelated to the study or the paper. Prior to the experiment, participants will go through a preliminary screening to ensure they possess the necessary level of expertise in software development. We will use a questionnaire to assess their experience, including questions about:

- Years of Experience: How many years have you been involved in software development?
- Experience with the On-Screen tool: How familiar are you with using IDEs and GitHub? (scale: None, small, medium, high)
- Experience with VR: How familiar are you with using VR? (scale: None, small, medium, high)
- Proficiency in Software Metrics: How would you rate your proficiency in understanding and using software metrics? (scale: None, Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced)
- Frequency of Use: How often do you use software development tools like IDEs and GitHub on your work duties? (scale: Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often, Always)
- Job position: What is your current job position?

The necessary level of expertise will be determined based on a combination of these factors. Participants should have at least intermediate familiarity with IDEs and GitHub and a minimum of 2 years of software development experience.

Participants will experience the experiment in two settings, with the order of the settings being randomly assigned:

On-screen: Participants will use a computer equipped with either GitLab, GitHub, or an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) capable of browsing the software system’s releases. These tools offer comprehensive features for visualizing code metrics across different releases, enabling users to navigate through versions and understand the codebase’s evolution. Expert consultation will be sought to finalize the best tool for this purpose.

Virtual Reality: Participants will immerse themselves in a VR scene (as described in Section II-B) using a Meta Quest 3 headset with a VR browser. Figure 3 depicts a participant during the VR experiment along with the screencast available for the supervisor’s reference.

Fig. 3: An example of the VR experiment setup

In each setting, participants will be presented with data from one of two projects, selected randomly. The order in which the projects are presented will also be randomized. While all participants will receive the same set of questions, each question will be presented in only one of the two settings and for one of the two projects.

Participants will provide their answers verbally, and the screens or VR scenes they interact with will be screencasted. Both the screencasts and the verbal responses will be recorded and transcribed. The experiment will be supervised by an observer who will provide assistance if necessary, using the screencast to monitor the participant’s progress and communicating via voice. If health guidelines necessitate isolated work, the supervisor will participate remotely, using a conferencing application to interact with the participant.

To ensure competency, participants will complete a questionnaire assessing their knowledge of relevant topics in software development. This will mitigate the risk of including participants who lack the necessary expertise. Additionally, participants will be asked about their prior experience with VR and the selected on-screen tool to ensure a balanced distribution of experience among the participants.

C. Tools

For data collection and analysis, we will utilize the GRIMOIRELAB platform. GRIMOIRELAB is a free, open-source toolset for software development analytics [39]. It includes modules that retrieve data from various types of software repositories [40], store it in a database, and then process and analyze it to produce a wide range of metrics. GRIMOIRELAB also features visualization modules that allow interaction with data through traditional on-screen web browsers. This platform is part of the Linux Foundation CHAOSS community.¹

Data generated by GRIMOIRELAB can be seamlessly integrated into BABIAXR, enabling the same pipeline to visualize

¹<https://chaoss.community>

data on 2D screens (e.g., GitHub or GitLab) and VR devices. BABIAXR, developed by the authors, is a toolset designed for 3D data visualization within web browsers. It leverages A-FRAME,² an open web framework for building 3D, augmented reality (AR), and VR experiences directly in the browser. A-FRAME extends HTML by introducing new entities, allowing developers to construct 3D scenes using familiar web development techniques. It is built on top of THREE.JS,³ which utilizes the WebGL API available in modern browsers.

BABIAXR extends A-FRAME by offering components for creating visualizations, simplifying data retrieval, and managing data (e.g., data filtering or mapping fields to visualization features). Scenes created with BABIAXR can be displayed on traditional screens or in VR devices, including consumer-grade headsets. Figure 1 provides an example of a scene built with BABIAXR. The toolset is open-source, with its source code available on GITLAB⁴ and installable via NPM.⁵

For the on-screen tool selection, we will use an IDE that provides access to data from the releases of the GitHub repository. This could be an installed IDE or the web-based GitHub interface, depending on what the developers use. The selected tool code metrics will be replicated in the VR experiment to ensure a fair comparison between the two settings.

D. Datasets

The datasets for the experiment will be sourced from two software projects with similar characteristics to avoid introducing bias. Key characteristics include project size, complexity, and the number of releases. This approach ensures that any differences observed in the experiment can be attributed to the visualization method rather than differences in the projects themselves. Given that the experiment runs in two different environments in two different rounds, having similar projects is the fairest approach to ensure a consistent basis for comparison.

E. Experimental Material

For the on-screen component of the experiment, we will use standard computers, as they are the primary tools for software developers. During the virtual reality phase, participants will use Meta Quest 3 VR headsets. The experimenter will provide these headsets, but participants with their own Meta Quest 3 headsets can use them if preferred. The VR scenes will be based on webXR standards, ensuring compatibility with any modern VR device with a web browser, making the experiment feasible in a remote setting if necessary.

F. Tasks

With the assistance of GRIMOIRELAB users and leveraging their expertise in software development project analysis, we have defined a series of tasks aimed at evaluating both the

accuracy of the solutions and the time taken to complete them. These tasks include:

- **Identifying Trends in Code Churn and Complexity:** Analyzing code churn and complexity metrics across various releases to identify patterns and significant changes.
- **Pinpointing Significant Changes in Code Quality Metric:** Examining releases to identify spikes or drops in code quality metrics, such as the number of bugs or code smells.
- **Assessing Code Maintainability Over Time:** Evaluating how maintainability metrics, such as cyclomatic complexity and technical debt, evolve over multiple releases.
- **Comparing Code Metrics Between Major Releases:** Comparing key code metrics between major software releases to understand the impact of new features or refactoring efforts.

These tasks focus on real-world scenarios where developers need to understand code metrics over time, such as identifying technical debt, planning refactoring efforts, and ensuring code quality. For example, analyzing code churn trends to decide when to refactor, or examining code complexity evolution to maintain code quality.

G. Hypotheses or Research Questions

The primary research question guiding our study is:

RQ: *“Is comprehension of a software system, through the visualization of its code metrics evolution, more effective in VR scenes compared to 2D screens?”*

This question tests the hypothesis that VR visualizations, which offer more spatial real estate, will enable better and quicker understanding of software metrics. Cognitive and spatial theories suggest that immersive environments enhance spatial awareness and memory retention, supporting our hypothesis. However, challenges such as perspective and distance perception remain.

To address the research question and test the hypothesis, we will focus on specific, measurable outcomes: the accuracy of the answers (as a proxy for correctness) and the time taken to provide these answers (as a proxy for efficiency). We will define a correct answer for each task and use an oracle to measure the distances from the provided answers to the correct ones. This leads to two refined research questions:

RQ1: *“Are answers more accurate in VR than on-screen?”* (alternative: more accurate on-screen)

RQ2: *“Are answers obtained faster in VR than on-screen?”* (alternative: faster on-screen)

To ensure the questions posed to participants effectively address these research questions, we will design them to yield numeric answers.

H. Variables

The independent variable that will be input for our experiment is the setting (on-screen tool in VR scene) in which each answer will be answered. Dependent variables will be

²A-FRAME: <https://aframe.io>

³THREE.JS: <https://threejs.org>

⁴<https://gitlab.com/babiaxr/aframe-babia-components>

⁵<https://npmjs.org/package/aframe-babia-components>

the answers that our subjects produce, and more concretely, how much deviated they are from the correct answer, and how long it took to produce them.

In more detail, for each Experiment Question (EQ), the variables are explained in Table I.

We will control for confounding variables by using regression models and other statistical techniques appropriate for our sample size. This approach will allow us to account for the influence of confounding variables without relying on potentially non-meaningful breakdowns of the data.

To measure the experience of participants, we will follow models such as the one proposed by Siegmund *et al.* [41], which includes various aspects of expertise such as years of experience, self-assessment of proficiency, and frequency of use. This comprehensive approach ensures a more accurate assessment of participants' expertise levels.

I. Design

To determine if VR is more effective than traditional 2D on-screen representations for visualizing software evolution, we will conduct a controlled experiment. We will adhere to the *ACM SIGSOFT Empirical Standards* [42] for experimental design, focusing on the quantitative methods for human experiments to meet all essential criteria and some desirable attributes. The experiment will be structured as a "One Factor, Two Level" design, where the independent variable is the visualization setting (either VR or on-screen). Participants will be randomly assigned to experience the settings in different orders (first VR or first on-screen), effectively creating two "One Factor, Two Level" sub-experiments.

J. Procedure

The study will also include a qualitative component, featuring semi-structured interviews with a subset of participants to gain insights into their experiences. To prepare for the study, we will set up and test the experimental settings in advance to identify and address any potential issues that could arise during the actual experiment.

K. Analysis Procedure

To evaluate the results, we will conduct statistical analyses on the task completion times and measure the significant differences using the most appropriate metrics for the sample size. We will also gather feedback on task difficulty, account for any timing deviations, and exclude outliers. Given the relatively small sample size of approximately 30 participants, it may be challenging to estimate the distribution of answers. Therefore, we will use non-parametric tests, which do not assume specific distributions, to assess whether the differences between the VR and on-screen settings are statistically significant.

We plan to use mixed linear models for our analysis, as recommended in prior research [43]. This model is well-suited for capturing within-subject correlations and accounting for the blocking variable, in this case, the group. By employing a mixed linear model, we can examine the effects of different

treatments while considering inherent variability and correlations within the data. This method has been successfully applied in our previous work [9], which followed a similar experimental design. This approach enables us to assess the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables, taking into account the unique characteristics of our experimental design.

IV. EXECUTION PLAN

Before conducting the experiment, to minimize potential bias due to previous experience with on-screen or VR settings, all subjects will undergo a brief training session. This training is designed to ensure participants understand how to use both the on-screen tool and the VR immersive scenes, as we anticipate that many subjects may not have prior experience with these technologies.

After the training, subjects will complete a demographic form to account for confounding variables. Following this, the experiment will commence with subjects being shown data from one of the two selected projects in a randomly assigned setting (either VR or on-screen). Subjects will then answer a series of questions (half of the total number, chosen randomly) one at a time, with each new question presented only after the previous one has been answered. Subsequently, each subject will repeat the process in the other setting with data from the second project.

At the conclusion of the experiment, subjects will complete a feedback form to provide insights into any issues encountered or suggestions for improvement. Once all data is collected, we will analyze it for any deviations or inconsistencies that may have occurred during the experiment.

V. THREATS TO VALIDITY

Internal validity is related to uncontrolled factors that can influence the effectiveness. In our case it pertains to:

- **Subjects.** We ensure that all participants have experience in different relevant topics about software development projects using a questionnaire, thus reducing the threat that they were not competent enough. We will also ask for their experience in VR and with the on-screen tool, so that we can later do the corresponding analysis to mitigate the threat of the influence of previous experience with them.
- **Tasks.** The choice of tasks (questions) could be biased in favor of one of the settings. We mitigate this threat by developing scenes that are valid for both VR and on-screen, with exactly the same tasks, so that the level of difficulty is as similar as possible. We also will include tasks that put both modes at a disadvantage: Tasks focused on precision could be easier on-screen, while tasks focused on locality could be easier in VR. Not controlled aspects (*e.g.*, the relative size of the buildings in VR) could have an influence on the results.
- **Training.** In both settings we will present a basic guide on how to use the settings for performing the tasks, we will offer texts about how the tool is used and how the interaction with the elements works. We also will investigate whether

Variable Type	Name	Description	Scale
Independent	Setting	Setting in which the question was answered by the subject. Subject answers after interacting with visualizations in a 2-D screen, or after interacting with visualizations immerse in virtual reality.	Categorical: "Screen" or "VR"
Dependent	TimeToAnswer	Time to answer the question. Number of seconds from the question is understood to the answer is produced.	Real number
Dependent	Error	Error in answering the question, with respect to the right answer. Relative error of the magnitude produced as answer with respect to the true value of that magnitude.	Real number
Confounding	ExperienceOnScreen	Overall experience with on-screen tool. This measures participants' familiarity with traditional 2D tools.	Categorical: "None", "small", "medium", "high"
Confounding	ExperienceVR	Overall experience with VR devices. This measures participants' familiarity with VR technology.	Categorical: "None", "small", "medium", "high"
Confounding	ExperienceSoftDev	Overall experience in software development. Question to the subject about their experience in software development, with a number of years of experience as answer.	Integer number
Confounding	Position	Position of the subject. This distinguishes between practitioners, academics, and students.	Categorical: "practitioner", "academic", "student"

TABLE I: Variables used in the experiment

a practical tutorial on how to interact with a VR headset could reduce the experience gap between VR and on-screen, improving the correctness of the VR tasks.

A. External validity

External validity relates to the generalizability of the results of the experiment. In our case it pertains to:

- **Sample Size.** The number of participants in the experiment can be relatively small. A larger sample would be needed to have more conclusive results. In order to determine if the results are statistically meaningful, we will run tests depending on this sample size.
- **Subjects.** We will mitigate the threat of subject representativeness by categorizing them, including their professional position and the years of experience in the main software development projects topics, obtaining a balanced mix of academics and professionals.
- **Target Systems.** Another threat is represented by the choice of the target systems. We will ensure that the two systems presented will have similar characteristics in order to mitigate the threat of having unbalanced systems that can interfere with the accuracy (correctness) and efficiency (completion time) of the responses.
- **Experimenter Effect.** The experimenters can be the authors of the research, which may influence any subjective aspect of the experiment. For example, task solutions may not be graded correctly. To mitigate this threat, another author can carry out part of the experiments as a supervisor. Both experimenters will build a model of the responses based on previous experiments in the literature. Even if we will try to mitigate this threat extensively, we cannot exclude all possible influences on the results of the experiment.
- **Time Measurement.** To mitigate the threat that task completion times are not affected by external factors, subjects will be required to answer via voice in both settings.

VI. CONTRIBUTIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

There is limited evidence regarding the effectiveness of VR for visualizing and interacting with complex software systems across their releases. As VR technology becomes more accessible, its adoption in software engineering and data visualization is expected to grow. It is essential to understand how these immersive environments impact practitioners compared to traditional 2D on-screen tools.

This study aims to provide insights from a controlled experiment comparing 2D on-screen visualization and VR immersive visualization, focusing on the accuracy and speed of comprehending high-level code metrics over multiple software releases. By doing so, we will uncover the strengths, applications, and challenges of both approaches, with a particular emphasis on VR visualization, which remains less explored and understood within the scientific community.

Additionally, we will offer valuable directions for practitioners, especially those developing visualization tools, by identifying effective elements and areas needing improvement. All software utilized in the experiment will be freely available under an open-source license, enabling other researchers and practitioners to examine, reuse, or modify it to suit their needs.

As VR technology continues to mature, we anticipate its increasing use in various domains, including software engineering. Regardless of whether our experiment's results are positive or negative, we believe it will pave the way for further research. Our experiment focuses on the visualization aspect of VR, but future studies could explore other software engineering activities (e.g., development, testing, profiling) and different perspectives (e.g., source code, diagrams).

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